

On Dynamic Cumulative Past Entropy Generating Function

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Abstract: In this paper we propose a dual concept of cumulative residual entropy generating function and studied its properties. The derivative of this new measure is the cumulative past entropy introduced by Di Crescenzo and Longobardi (2009). We also define the dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function and give its properties. It is shown that the proposed measure uniquely determines the distribution. Finally we characterized certain lifetime distributions using the functional form of the proposed measure.

Keywords: Power distributions, Past Entropy, Cumulative Past Entropy, Reliability.

1. Introduction

Entropy is an important concept in the field of information theory and Shannon (1948) was the first who formally introduced the concept of entropy. Let X be an absolutely continuous non-negative random variable with probability density function (p.d.f) f , the Shannon's entropy is defined as

$$H(X) = - \int_0^{\infty} f(x) \log f(x) dx. \tag{1}$$

Suppose X represents the lifetime of a unit, then $H(X)$ can be used for measuring the associated expected uncertainty. Rao et. al. (2004) introduced a new measure of uncertainty based on the survival function of the non-negative random variable X with distribution function (d.f) $F(x)$, called cumulative residual entropy and obtained some properties. It is defined as,

$$\xi(X) = - \int_0^{\infty} \bar{F}(x) \log \bar{F}(x) dx, \tag{2}$$

where the survival function $\bar{F}(x) = 1 - F(x)$. This measure is considered to be more stable since d.f. is more regular than p.d.f and also the d.f. exists even cases where density does not. For more properties and applications of this measure one can refer Rao et. al. (2004).

Asadi and Zohrevand (2007) considered the dynamic cumulative residual entropy function and is defined as

$$\xi_X(t) = - \int_t^{\infty} \frac{\bar{F}(x)}{\bar{F}(t)} \log \frac{\bar{F}(x)}{\bar{F}(t)} dx. \tag{3}$$

Di Crescenzo and Longobardi (2009) introduced cumulative past entropy, which is given by

$$\bar{\xi}_X = - \int_0^{\infty} F(x) \log F(x) dx. \tag{4}$$

In many realistic situations, uncertainty is not necessarily related to the future but can also refer to the past. In such situations Di Crescenzo and Longobardi (2009) introduced dynamic cumulative past entropy, which is given by

$$\bar{\xi}_X(t) = - \int_0^t \frac{F(x)}{F(t)} \log \frac{F(x)}{F(t)} dx. \tag{5}$$

It is well known that the successive derivatives of the moment generating function (m.g.f) at point zero give the successive moments of a probability distribution, if these moments exists. In a correspondence, Golomb (1966) introduced the information generating function of a probability distribution namely, entropy generating function and is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 B(s) &= \int_0^\infty f^s(x)dx, s \geq 0, s \neq 1 \tag{6} \\
 &= E[\exp(1 - s)l_X(f)], \text{ where } l_X(f) = -\log f(x) \\
 &= M_{l_X(f)}(1 - s),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $M_X(S) = E(e^{sX})$ denotes the m.g.f of the random variable X . Table 0 gives the expression of $B(s)$ for some well-known distributions.

Table 1: $B(s)$ for some well-known distributions.

Distribution	$\bar{F}(x)$	$B(s)$
GPD	$(1 + \frac{ax}{b})^{-(1+\frac{1}{a})}; x > 0$	$\frac{(a + 1)^s}{b^{s-1}a \left[(2 + \frac{1}{a})s - 1 \right]}$
Power distribution	$1 - x^c; 0 < x < 1.$	$\frac{c^s}{(c - 1)s + 1}$
Gamma	Incomplete gamma	$\frac{\Gamma(p - 1)s + 1}{(\Gamma p)^s m^{1-s} s^{(p-1)s+1}}$
Pareto II	$(1 + \frac{x}{a})^{-b}$	$(\frac{b}{s})^s \frac{a}{(b + 1)s - 1}$
Beta (α, β)	$1 - \text{BetaRegularized}(\alpha, \beta)$	$\frac{(\frac{1}{\text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)})^s \Gamma[1 + s(\alpha - 1)]\Gamma[1 + s(\beta - 1)]}{\Gamma[2 + s(-2 + \alpha + \beta)]}$

The first derivative of the entropy generating function of a probability distribution at $s = 1$ gives the negative Shannon’s entropy measure.

Motivated with the importance of $B(s)$ in generating Shannon’s entropy function and to explore its usefulness for the past lifetime of the random variable, we introduced the notion of cumulative past entropy generating function and studied its properties. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we propose cumulative past entropy generating function and study its important properties. In Section 3, we study dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function and its important properties. In section 4, we prove some characterizations results for power function.

2 Cumulative Past Entropy Generating Function and its properties

Here we are introducing a dual concept of cumulative residual entropy generating function and is defined as,

$$\bar{C}_s(X) = \int_0^\infty (F(x))^s dx \tag{7}$$

which measures the information concerning past lifetime.

The first derivative of $\bar{C}_s(X)$ at $s = 1$, and put negative sign we get cumulative past entropy.

2.1 Properties

Here we show that $\bar{C}_s(X)$ is a shift independent measure.

Property 1 If $Y = aX + b$, with $a > 0$ and $b \geq 0$, then

$$\bar{C}_s(Y) = a \cdot \bar{C}_s(X). \tag{8}$$

Proof. The result follows from $F_{aX+b}(x) = F_X\left(\frac{x-b}{a}\right)$ and $\bar{C}_s(X)$.

Remark 2.1 From the above property, we have if $a = 1$, $\bar{C}_s(Y) = \bar{C}_s(X)$.

Like the proportional hazards model, Gupta et. al. (2007) proposed a dual model called proportional reversed hazards model, defined by the relationship between distribution functions as

$$F_\theta(x) = [F(x)]^\theta; \theta > 0, \theta \neq 1, x \in R.$$

Property 2 The statement, $\bar{C}_s(X_\theta^*) = \bar{C}_{s\theta}(X)$ hold.

$$\bar{C}_s(X_\theta^*) = \int_0^\infty (F_\theta(x))^s dx \tag{9}$$

$$= \int_0^\infty (F(x))^{\theta s} dx \tag{10}$$

$$= \bar{C}_{s\theta}(X). \tag{11}$$

Example 2.1 Suppose X follows power function with

$$F(t) = \left(\frac{t}{b}\right)^c; 0 < t < b, c > 0,$$

then

$$\bar{C}_s(X_\theta^*) = \frac{b}{s\theta c + 1}$$

and

$$\bar{C}_{s\theta}(X) = \frac{b}{s\theta c + 1}$$

so

$$\bar{C}_s(X_\theta^*) = \bar{C}_{s\theta}(X).$$

Property 3 Let $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$ be independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.) random variables representing lifetime of the components in parallel system with p.d.f $f(x)$ and d.f $F(x)$. The lifetime of the system is then $X_{(n)} = \max\{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n\}$ with d.f $F_{X_n} = (F(x))^n$. Here X_i and $X_{(n)}$ satisfy the condition for reversed hazard model. By direct calculation we get $\bar{C}_s(X_{(n)}) = \bar{C}_{ns}(X)$.

3 Dynamic Cumulative Past Entropy Generating Function and its properties

In many situations, especially in survival studies, the data are right truncated. Motivated by this, in this section we define the dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function and also we give its uniqueness property.

Definition 3.1 If X denotes the lifetime of a component or of living organism, then the dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function of X is defined as

$$\bar{C}_s(X; t) = \int_0^t \left(\frac{F(x)}{F(t)}\right)^s dx; s > 1 \tag{12}$$

where $F(t)$ is the cumulative distribution function.

3.1 Properties

Property 1 When $s = 1, \bar{C}_s(X; t) = \bar{m}(t)$, the mean inactivity time.

Property 2 $-\frac{d}{dt} \bar{C}_s(X; t) |_{s=1}$ is the dynamic cumulative past entropy measure.

Property 3 For any non-negative random variable $X, Y = aX + b$ where $a > 0, b \geq 0$, then $\bar{C}_s(Y; t) = a \cdot \bar{C}_s(X; \frac{t-b}{a})$.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{C}_s(Y; t) &= \int_0^t \left(\frac{F_Y(x)}{F(t)} \right)^s dx \\ &= a \cdot \int_0^{\frac{t-b}{a}} \left(\frac{F_Y(u)}{F(t)} \right)^s du \\ &= a \cdot \bar{C}_s \left(X; \frac{t-b}{a} \right); \quad t \geq b. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the proof.

Remark 3.1 From the above property, we have

1. If $a = 1$, then $\bar{C}_s(Y; t) = \bar{C}_s(X; t - b)$.
2. If $b = 0$, then $\bar{C}_s(Y; t) = a \cdot \bar{C}_s(X; \frac{t}{a})$.

Property 4 Using the relationship with reversed hazard rate

$$(F(t))^s \cdot \bar{C}_s(X; t) = \int_0^t (F(x))^s dx.$$

Differentiating the above equation w.r.t. 't',

$$\begin{aligned} s(F(t))^{s-1} f(t) \cdot \bar{C}_s(X; t) + \bar{C}_s'(X; t) (F(t))^s &= (F(t))^s \\ s \cdot \lambda(t) \bar{C}_s(X; t) + \bar{C}_s'(X; t) &= 1. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where, $\lambda(t)$ is the reversed hazard rate. That is,

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{f(t)}{F(t)} \text{ and } \lambda(t) = \frac{1 - \bar{C}_s'(X; t)}{s \cdot \bar{C}_s(X; t)}.$$

That is,

$$\frac{d}{dt} \log F(t) = \frac{1 - \bar{C}_s'(X; t)}{s \cdot \bar{C}_s(X; t)}$$

Therefore,

$$F(x) = \exp \left(- \int_x^\infty \left(\frac{1 - \bar{C}_s'(X; t)}{s \cdot \bar{C}_s(X; t)} \right) dt \right).$$

This result shows that the knowledge of $C_s(X; t)$ enables us to determine the distribution uniquely.

The following Theorem shows that the dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function determines uniquely the underlying distribution function.

Theorem 3.1 Let X be the non-negative random variable having density function $f(x)$ and distribution function $F(x)$. Assume that $\bar{C}_s(F; t)$ is increasing in t . Then this measure uniquely determines the distribution function F .

Proof. Suppose that $F(x)$ and $G(x)$ are distribution functions such that

$$\bar{C}_s(F; t) = \bar{C}_s(G; t). \tag{14}$$

That is,

$$\frac{1}{(F(t))^s} \int_0^t (F(x))^s dx = \frac{1}{(G(t))^s} \int_0^t (G(x))^s dx. \tag{15}$$

Differentiating w.r.t 't',

$$\begin{aligned} & (F(t))^{-s} \cdot (F(t))^s + \int_0^t (F(x))^s dx \cdot (-s)(F(t))^{-s-1}f(t) \\ & = (G(t))^{-s} \cdot (G(t))^s + \int_0^t (G(x))^s dx \cdot (-s)(G(t))^{-s-1}g(t). \end{aligned}$$

That is,

$$\lambda_1(t) \cdot \bar{C}_s(F; t) = \lambda_2(t) \cdot \bar{C}_s(G; t) \tag{16}$$

where, $\lambda_1(t) = \frac{f(t)}{F(t)}$ and $\lambda_2(t) = \frac{g(t)}{G(t)}$ are the reversed hazard rates.

$$\lambda_1(t) = \lambda_2(t)F(t) = G(t).$$

So $\bar{C}_s(F; t)$ uniquely determines the distribution.

4 Characterization Results

Now the characterization result for power function distribution based on dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function is given below. Also noted that uniform distribution is a special case.

Theorem 4.1 *Let X be a non-negative continuous random variable with d.f F(x), reversed hazard rate λ(x) and the dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function $\bar{C}_s(F; t)$, then the relationship*

$$\bar{C}_s(F; t) = (\lambda(t))^{-1} \cdot K \tag{17}$$

where K is a positive constant, holds if and only if F(x) is the d.f of power distribution,

$$F(x) = \left(\frac{x}{b}\right)^a \tag{18}$$

Proof. Assume that $\lambda(t) \cdot \bar{C}_s(F; t) = K$. holds
Differentiating w.r.t 't',

$$\lambda(t) \cdot \bar{C}_s'(F; t) + \bar{C}_s(F; t) \lambda'(t) = 0. \tag{19}$$

Then

$$\lambda(t)[1 - s \cdot \lambda(t) \bar{C}_s(F; t)] + \bar{C}_s(F; t) \cdot \lambda'(t) = 0.$$

The above equation becomes,

$$\lambda(t)[1 - sK] + \bar{C}_s(F; t) \cdot \lambda'(t) = 0$$

$$\lambda(t)[1 - sK] + K \cdot \frac{\lambda'(t)}{\lambda(t)} = 0$$

$$-\frac{\lambda'(t)}{(\lambda(t))^2} = \frac{1-sK}{K}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda(t)} \right) = \frac{1-sK}{K}$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda(t)} = \left(\frac{1-sK}{K} \right) t + c$$

Therefore,

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{1}{bt+c}; b = \frac{1-sK}{K}.$$

Using the equation, $F(x) = \exp(-\int_x^\infty \lambda(t)dt)$, we conclude that X follows power distribution. Conversely assume that X follows power distribution. By direct computation

$$\bar{C}_s(F; t) = \frac{t}{as+1} = \frac{t}{a(s+\frac{1}{a})} = k \cdot \frac{1}{\lambda(t)}$$

That is,

$$\bar{C}_s(F; t) = (\lambda(t))^{-1}k.$$

Hence the theorem.

The following theorem provides a characterization for power function distribution using a relationship between $\bar{C}_s(F; t)$ and mean inactivity time.

Theorem 4.2 *If X is a non-negative random variable admitting an absolutely continuous d.f $F(x)$, then the relationship*

$$\bar{C}_s(F; t) = k \cdot \bar{m}(t); k > 0 \tag{20}$$

where $\bar{m}(t)$ is the mean inactivity time of X holds for every $t > 0$ if and only if $X \sim$ Power distribution.

Proof. Assume $\bar{C}_s(F; t) = k \cdot \bar{m}(t)$. Differentiating w.r.t 't',

$$\bar{C}'_s(F; t) = k \cdot \bar{m}'(t). \tag{21}$$

The relation $\bar{m}'(t) = 1 - \bar{m}(t) \cdot \lambda(t)$. The equation becomes

$$1 - s \cdot \lambda(t) \bar{C}_s(F; t) = k[1 - \bar{m}(t) \cdot \lambda(t)]$$

$$1 - sk \cdot \lambda(t) \bar{m}(t) = k[1 - \bar{m}(t) \cdot \lambda(t)]$$

$$1 - k = \lambda(t) \bar{m}(t) [sk - k]$$

$$1 - \bar{m}'(t) = \frac{1-k}{sk-k}$$

$$\bar{m}'(t) = 1 - \left(\frac{1-k}{sk-k}\right) = \frac{sk-1}{sk-k} = p, \text{ a constant.}$$

$\bar{m}(t)$ is linear in t

the distribution is power.

Conversely assume that $X \sim$ Power function distribution. By direct computation,

$$\bar{C}_s(F; t) = \frac{t}{as+1} = k \cdot \bar{m}(t); k = \frac{a+1}{as+1}$$

Hence the proof.

The next theorem provides a characterization result for power distribution based on the functional form of dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function.

Theorem 4.3 *Let X be a non-negative continuous random variable with d.f $F(x)$. The dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function is a linear function of 't' if and only if X follows power function distribution.*

Proof. Assume that $\bar{C}_s(F; t) = a + bt; b \neq 0$. Then, $\bar{C}'_s(F; t) = b$.

From the relationship with reversed hazard rate,

$$1 - s \cdot \lambda(t) \bar{C}_s(F; t) = b$$

$$\therefore \bar{C}_s(F; t) = \frac{1-b}{s \cdot \lambda(t)}$$

$$a + bt = \frac{1-b}{s \cdot \lambda(t)}$$

$$(a + bt) \lambda(t) = \frac{1-b}{s}.$$

Differentiating w.r.t 't',

$$(a + bt) \lambda'(t) + \lambda(t) \cdot b = 0$$

$$-\frac{\lambda'(t)}{\lambda(t)} = \frac{b}{a+bt}$$

$$-\frac{d}{dt}(\log \lambda(t)) = \frac{b}{a+bt}$$

Integrating,

$$\log(\lambda(t))^{-1} = \log(a + bt) + \log c$$

Therefore,

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{1}{(a+bt)c}$$

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{1}{k+dt}; \quad k = ac, d = bc.$$

This is the reversed hazard rate of power function distribution since the distribution uniquely

determined by the reversed hazard rate, $X \sim$ Power function distribution.

Conversely assume that, $X \sim$ Power distribution. By direct computation, we get,
 $\bar{C}_s(F; t) = \frac{t}{as+1}$ is linear in 't'. Hence the theorem.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we propose a dual concept of cumulative residual entropy generating function and studied its properties. The negative of the derivative of this new measure is the cumulative past entropy introduced by Di Crescenzo and Longobardi (2009). We also define the dynamic cumulative past entropy generating function and give its properties. It is shown that the proposed measure uniquely determines the distribution. Finally we characterized power distribution using the relationship between functional form of the proposed measure and some basic reliability concepts.

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